

Comparative study on Birth rate of India, China and USA (1960-2022)

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Received: Aug 9 , 2025 **Accepted:** Sep 5, 2025 **Published:** Sep 11, 2025

Abstract. There were contrast birth rates for the various countries in which the populous have been compared. The objective of this research is of role play of birth rate and how it affects the vital events like fertility rate, life expectancy at birth and infant mortality rate and death rates. The secondary source of data has been collected from the United Nations of Population Division (UNPD). The available vital statistics has been taken for the period, 1960-2022. These data has been analyzed and observed the trends of birth rate in India, China and USA. Similarly, fertility rate and birth rate are also observed to be very high in India as compared to top countries like USA and China. The statistical analysis has been done for the data of birth rate. Correlation and regression models have been fitted; with the help of multiple linear regressions further, it can be extended to Path analyses. The China has shown a significant change and it has been maintaining a consistent growth of life expectancy at birth, controlling the infant mortality rate and birth rate. It has followed by better precautions for the well-being of country as compared to other countries like India and USA.

Keywords: Birth rate, life expectancy at birth, infant mortality rate, India, correlation, regression and path analysis.

1 Introduction

Prevalence birth missing in fertility histories were estimated and studied their associated facts [1]. In this research paper explained, the association between fertility rates on uncertainty of economic policies, government financial crisis and confidence of consumer [2]. The China has been focused one-child policy era. For this reason, fertility had declined during the 1970's. Also, investigated the possibility of the sex ratio's began raised during this period. The literature provided first, they focused on the subset of couples among whom they have demand for the sons were predicted to be very strong [3]. The methodology used like Cluster Analysis and line regression analysis. It can be identified the patterns in trajectories of working-age population to detect associated demographic factors. Performed analysis for 148 countries by using UN World population prospects 2022 data. Noticeable changes found in fertility between countries by the sharing of working-age population are associated with population and migration [4].

1.1 Review of literature

The World fertility rates have been observed in the mid-twentieth Century, there were more developed regions and less developed regions. There were two categories created by United Nations Population Division. "The more developed regions were United States of America, Canada, Europe, Australia, Japan and New Zealand. The less developed regions were Asia excluding Japan, Latin America and Caribbean, Africa and Oceania excluding Australia and New Zealand" [5].

China's fertility rate has been decreased to lower levels and the (CFR) Completed Cohort Fertility rate showed significant. Marriage postponement results in low birth rates and fertility rates [6]. It is owing to the low birth rate in China, the population growth rate has been declining steadily. The Census of China indicates that the population has been ageing to old persons because of increased life expectancy by the low birth rate [7]. China has challenges associated with adjusting to population decline and the increased size of the older population. Fertility was also observed to be lower in China. The characteristics of the people, such as productivity and education, are more optimistic and have a very low birth rate [8]. The teen birth rates in the USA had observed over the last two decades. There was a dramatic decline; it reached a lower of 31.3 percent in 2011 and higher up to 61.8% in 1991 as it was 49 %. In the last four years of the period, it was observed to be 1/3 part declined. (The teenage was between 15 to 19) [9].

The present research examines the changes in the demographic structure, decline to lower youth dependency, the contribution of the fertility rate which have helped fuel China's financial status since 1989. Also, significant economic growth was found in demographic behaviors through expectation of life, age of marriage and birth rate [10]. The study of factors, related to fertility rate in China over the 1952 to 2000 period. The dependent variable in our fertility model was real per capita income, infant mortality rate, female labor force and female literacy participation rates [11]. This search

focused on comparisons between India's states as they revealed firsthand information on couples protected from unwanted pregnancies by family planning methods. The variables associated with fertility in India are female literacy, infant mortality rate, poverty, expenditure on health and family welfare, female age at marriage and income [12]. The approach of analyzing and forecasting age-specific mortality procedures are mainly three i). Analyze age-specific data directly (ii) Analyze each cause-specific mortality series separately (iii) analyze cause-specific mortality series. It has utilized linear models and the three approaches have given close results [13].

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Methodology

The secondary data had taken through the sources of World development indicators and the statistical reports of the UNPD. The vital statistics; expectation of life at birth, Infant mortality rate and birth rates were taken for the period from 1960-2022. The data has been analyzed for India, China and the USA. Calculated the multiple-correlations and fitted trend lines for the birth rate. All the three countries' birth rates showed as linear and second-degree polynomial equations. The correlations, multiple regression models and standardized coefficients have been found with the help of R-Code. The charts are observed for (BR) birth rate, infant mortality rate (IMR) and life expectancy at birth (e^0) in India, China and USA. With the help of multiple regressions, the Path models were built. In this procedure, computed net effect and interaction or joint effects; and then component analysis. This was presented in the result tables I, II and III.

Pattern of Correlation between variables

If two variables are measured for each of the samples, the relationship between these variables can be studied with the use of correlation and regression procedures. Correlation helps to assess the degree of association between two variables. The relationship between the variable values, say x and y, can be observed by plotting the x values on the X-axis and the corresponding values of y on the Y-axis. The graph obtained after plotting the x and y value pairs are known as a scatter diagram. The scatter diagrams help visualize the state of the relationship between variables, say x and y. There are various types of relationships existing; that can have a relationship resembling a straight line or a curve. There can also be no relationship existing between variables and these, connection can be positive or negative also.

Regression procedure

The regression procedure is also known as the procedure for prediction. We may come across many studies with missing values. Regression procedures are helpful for the prediction of the missing values. These procedures are also utilized for the forecasting of future events. The correlation between variables, say x and y quantified by regression procedure with an equation such as $Y=a+bX$. This equation is also known as the linear regression equation ¹⁴.

Path analysis

During the 1920's Path analysis technique was found by Sewell Wright. It has been developed for the need of quantitative development of genetics. Further, it was developed by Duncan and Land. The technique helps to build an ordinary multiple regression lines. The approaches of methodology were only to sets of relationship through the variables, which are additive, causal and linear. Multiple regression equation is being affected by response and predictor variables. Also, one or more intervening variables affect the response variable. This causal relationship is more helpful for the analysis of the factors in the procedure of Path analysis¹⁵.

Materials

Source of the data

The required secondary data has been pooled through the source of the United Nations Population Division (UNPD). Available demographic variables, important events like birth rate, death rate, infant mortality rate under-five mortality rate and life expectancy at birth have been taken from the year 1960 to 2022 for India.

The statistical data is being collected through the development of data group, which support the throughout the world. It coordinates all the essential statistical data collection and also maintains a number of macro and micro sectors of databases. The World Bank group was advised by expert committee to collect the standard data, compilation and dissemination of data to support the users that they must believe in the quality and integrity as well.

Source <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.CBRT.IN?locations=IN>

3 Results and Discussion

The three countries (India, China and USA) are being fitted trend lines and have observed that, the India has been followed by a linear trend ($y = -0.451x + 928.65$) with $R^2 = 0.98$, which is the best model fit. China and USA have been followed by Second-degree polynomial equations ($y = 0.0045x^2 - 18.28x + 18621$ and $y = 0.0017x^2 - .064x + 7179.6$) with $R^2 = 0.76$, and 0.78 are the best fitted models. All three countries are observed to have life expectancy at birth, which has been increasing in positive trend, whereas birth rate and infant mortality rates have been decreasing in negative trends.

Table 1. The correlation between birth rate, life expectancy and infant mortality in India.

	Birth rate	Life expectancy	IMR
Birth rate	1.00	-0.99	0.99
Life expectancy	-0.99	1.00	-1.00
(IMR) Infant mortality rate	0.99	-1.00	1.00

Regression Models for India

Model-I $Y = 87.748 + (-0.9806) X_2 + \epsilon$ (1)

Model-II $Y = 13.442 + 0.189594 X_3 + \epsilon$ (2)

Model-III $Y = 7.1706 + 0.08288 X_2 + 0.2055X_3 + \epsilon$ (3)

Fig. 1. Path model diagram of birth rate (Y₁), life expectancy at birth (X₂) and Infant mortality rate (X₃) for India (1960-2021).

Y₁=Birth rate of India, 1960-2021.

X₂=Life expectancy at birth

X₃= Infant mortality rate

The statistical model adopted for this study is a simple linear model.

$Y_1 = P_{12}X_2 + P_{13}X_3$ (P₁₂, P₁₃ and P₂₃ are called path coefficients)

P₁₂=0.08342, P₁₃=1.0745 (from standardized coefficients)

and R²_{1,23}= 0.9781 (R-square unadjusted)

R_u= sqrt (1- R²_{1,23}) = $\sqrt{1 - 0.9781}$

R_u= 0.1479 (R_u is the residual path coefficient)

$$R^2 = P_{12}^2 + P_{13}^2 + 2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$$

Result table-I. Component analysis of the coefficient of determination $R^2_{1,23}$

Details	Component	Amount	R^2 (%)	Percentage R^2
Net effect				
Due to X_2	P_{12}^2	0.006	0.695	0.708
Due to X_3	P_{13}^2	1.154	115.455	117.542
Total of net effects		1.161	116.150	118.251
Joint effect				
Due to X_2X_3	$2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$	-0.179	-17.926	-18.251
Total of joint effects		-0.179	-17.926	-18.251
Total multiple Determination	$R^2_{1,23}$	0.982	98.223	100.00

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Table 2. The correlation between birth rate, life expectancy at birth, and infant mortality in China.

	Birth rate	Life expectancy	Infant mortality rate
Birth rate	1.000	-0.928	0.932
Life expectancy	-0.928	1.000	-0.990
Infant mortality rate	0.932	-0.990	1.000

Regression Models for China.

Model-I $Y = 79.8189 + (-0.8949) X_2 + \epsilon$ (4)

Model-II $Y = 8.2994 + (0.2682) X_3 + \epsilon$ (5)

Model-III: $Y = 28.1123 + (-0.2483) X_2 + 0.1948 X_3 + \epsilon$ (6)

Fig. 2. Path model diagram of birth rate (Y_1), life expectancy at birth (X_2) and Infant mortality rate (X_3) for China (1960-2021).

Y_1 =Birth rate of China, 1969-2021.

X_2 =Life expectancy at birth

X_3 = Infant mortality rate

The statistical model adopted for this study is a simple linear model.

$$Y_1 = P_{12}X_2 + P_{13}X_3$$

$P_{12} = -0.258, P_{13} = 0.677$ (from standardized coefficients)

and $R^2_{1,23} = 0.870$

$$R_u = \sqrt{1 - R^2_{1,23}} = \sqrt{1 - 0.870}$$

$$R_u = 0.360$$

$$R^2 = P_{12}^2 + P_{13}^2 + 2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$$

Result table-II. Component analysis of the coefficient of determination $R^2_{1,23}$

Details	Component	Amount	R^2 (%)	Percentage R^2
Net effect				
Due to X_2	P_{12}^2	0.066	6.656	7.644
Due to X_3	P_{13}^2	0.458	45.832	52.637
Total of net effects		0.524	52.489	60.281
Joint effect				
Due to X_2X_3	$2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$	0.345	34.583	39.718
Total of joint effects		0.345	34.583	39.718
Total multiple Determination	$R^2_{1,23}$	0.870	87.073	100.00

Table 3. The correlation between Birth rates, life expectancy and infant mortality in USA

	Birth rate	Life Expectancy	Infant mortality rate
Birth rate	1.000	-0.837	0.881
Life expectancy	-0.837	1.000	-0.962
Infant mortality rate	0.881	-0.962	1.000

Regression models for USA

Model-I $Y = 79.8189 + (-0.8949) X_2 + \varepsilon$ (7)

Model-II $Y = 10.8444 + (0.3868) X_3 + \varepsilon$ (8)

Model-III $Y = 0.2946 + (0.1317) X_2 + 0.4457 X_3 + \varepsilon$ (9)

Fig. 2. Path model diagram of birth rate (Y₁), life expectancy at birth (X₂) and Infant mortality rate (X₃) for USA (1960-2021).

Y₁=Birth rate of USA, 1969-2021.

X₂=Life expectancy

X₃= Infant mortality rate

The statistical model adopted for this study is a simple linear model.

$$Y_1 = P_{12}X_2 + P_{13}X_3$$

$$P_{12} = 0.1396482, P_{13} = 1.01543 \text{ (from standardized coefficients)}$$

$$\text{and } R^2_{1,23} = 0.7779$$

$$R_u = \sqrt{1 - R^2_{1,23}} = \sqrt{1 - 0.7779}$$

$$R_u = 0.4712$$

$$R^2 = P_{12}^2 + P_{13}^2 + 2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$$

Result table-III. Component analysis of the coefficient of determination $R^2_{1,23}$

Details	Component	Amount	R^2 (%)	Percentage R^2
Net effect				
Due to X_2	P_{12}^2	0.019	1.950	2.509
Due to X_3	P_{13}^2	1.031	103.109	132.668
Total of net effects		1.050	105.059	135.177
Joint effect				
Due to X_2X_3	$2P_{12}P_{13}r_{23}$	-0.272	-27.340	-35.099
Total of joint effects		-0.272	-27.340	-35.099
Total multiple Determination	$R^2_{1,23}$	0.777	77.719	100.00

From the Result table-I, table-II and table-III are observed to have; the net effect due to (X_3) infant mortality rate (IMR) percentage of R^2 , 117.542, 52.637, and 132.668 are being followed by India, China and USA. The highest percentage of R^2 has been found by 132.668 represented in Result table-III. Similarly, due to (X_2X_3) variables, which are known to be the interaction or joint effect percentage of R^2 , -18.251, 39.718 and -35.099, followed by India, China and USA are from Result table-I to table-III. Among these, the highest percentage of R^2 has shown (in negative value) -35.099 is from Result table-III. The interaction effect of China's percentage of R^2 is positive, 39.718 from Result table-II, because the birth rate was shown consistent as compared to India and the USA. The results were revealed by the path analysis, the China has been maintaining consistent rules to control the birth rate. Suggest to govt. of India to follow these restrictions as they have followed by China, further steps need to be taken to control birth rate of India. Similarly, government has to suggest the instructions to control the birth rates.

4 Conclusion

The birth rate was controlled by bearing one child, having a female education, increasing age for marriages of male and female, the encouragement of family planning participation of both women and men. The high birth and fertility rates happened, association of health and wealth problems, their economic status, living low standards and less educational background of male and female. Also, high birth rates and fertility rates leads to high (IMR) infant mortality rates. The government has to enforce the minimum age of marriage like to increase from more than 18 years and 21 years for female and male. It has to address and stress female literacy and women's empowerment. They have to educate the people through the media like television, radio and Newspaper while giving the advertisement about family planning. Also, it has to increase the family planning services. Meanwhile, it has to be given more offers for sterilization to male. To increase the availability of contraceptives like pills, condoms and awareness of sex. This leads to control the birth rate or fertility rates in India. China, USA and every developed country have been initiated to control the population and birth rate as well.

Acknowledgments. The availability of data on the UNPD Website and can be easily downloadable for the research purpose. There is no fund is being given for this research. It is of interest to do the researchers only.

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